

A New Method for the Separation of Lead from Zinc and their Subsequent Estimations.

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It has been found by Das-Gupta, Roy and Sil (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 657) that hydrogen peroxide and ammonium hydroxide can effect a quantitative precipitation of lead even in presence of nitrates and acetates of ammonia and alkalis, provided that the concentration of the salt present does not exceed the limits stated therein.

With increasing amounts of ammonium nitrate in solutions of lead nitrate, the colour of the lead precipitate, found to be mixtures of lead peroxide and oxide in different proportions, varies gradually from orange to yellow. These precipitates, on being gently heated over a small flame or in a crucible bath (*i.e.*, placing the crucible containing the precipitate on an asbestos ring fitted inside a bigger crucible near its bottom and then heating the latter strongly), give a yellow residue which on analysis was found to be pure lead monoxide. This observation together with the quantitative precipitation of lead within certain concentrations of ammonium nitrate (4 g. per 100 c.c. solution) serves as a basis for the estimation of lead in presence of ammonium nitrate by hydrogen peroxide and ammonia. There was no action, however, of hydrogen peroxide and ammonia on zinc salts, specially zinc nitrate, in presence of an excess of ammonia, and therefore after precipitation of lead, zinc can be estimated by the usual method.

EXPERIMENTAL.

To a solution of lead nitrate, dilute nitric acid (1 or 2 drops) was first added and the solution was considerably diluted and then 2 c.c. of 3% hydrogen peroxide and 2 c.c. of concentrated ammonia added for 0.1 g. of lead, taking care that the total volume was always above 100 c.c. The voluminous precipitate so obtained was then heated on a water-bath ($\frac{1}{2}$ – $1\frac{1}{2}$ hr.; longer in presence of ammonium nitrate), when it was converted into the crystalline state,

The precipitate was then filtered, washed with hot water till the wash-water was free from nitrate, dried and then heated gently over a small flame or in a crucible bath (*vide supra*) when a yellow residue was left behind. The residue was analysed by first converting it into the nitrate and then into sulphate. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

NH ₄ NO ₃ Soln. (8%) added.	Wt. of residue.	Wt. of PbSO ₄ from the residue.	% of lead in the residue.
5 c.c.	0·1050 g.	0·1427 g.	92·83
10	0·0991	0·1347	92·85
15	0·1258	0·1710	92·84
20	0·0952	0·1293	92·77
30	0·1144	0·1554	92·80
40	0·1131	0·1534	92·66
50	0·0470	0·0638	92·74
0	0·0848	0·1152	92·81
0	0·0990	0·1356	92·82
0	0·1123	0·1526	92·83

The above results show that the yellow residue is purely PbO, as the percentage of lead contained in it corresponds to the theoretical value 92·83.

Estimation of Lead in presence of Ammonium Nitrate.

Exactly 16·55 g of lead nitrate were dissolved in 500 c.c. of water. In this solution, as a check, lead was also estimated as PbSO₄ and as Pb₅O₇, 3H₂O, which gave 0·1037 g. and 0·1032 g. of lead respectively in 5 c.c. of the solution; whereas from the weight of lead nitrate taken, lead present in 5 c.c. of the solution is 0·1035 g. or 0·1115 g. as PbO.

5 C.c. of this lead nitrate solution were taken and mixed with different amounts of ammonium nitrate solution. From the mixture lead is precipitated by hydrogen peroxide and ammonia and the precipitate was washed, dried and then converted into yellow PbO and weighed as such. (For particulars, *vide infra*. The results are given in Table II).

TABLE II.

Pb (NO₃)₂ soln. = 5 c.c. Wt. of PbO present = 0.1115 g.

NH ₄ NO ₃ soln. (8%) in c.c.	5	10	15	20	30	40	50
Wt. of PbO found in g.	0.1113	0.1113	0.1115	0.1117	0.1114	0.2118	0.1112

Separation of Lead from Zinc and their Estimations.

About 20.5 g. of zinc nitrate were dissolved in 500 c.c. of water. From this solution zinc was estimated as ZnNH₄PO₄ and also as Zn₂P₂O₇ (*vide* Treadwell and Hall, Vol. II). 10 C.c. of the solution gave 0.2470 g. of ZnNH₄PO₄ and 0.2111 g. of Zn₂P₂O₇.

Measured volumes of lead and zinc nitrate solutions were mixed together and the total volume made up to 100 c.c. Lead was precipitated from this solution with requisite amount of hydrogen peroxide and excess of ammonia. The solution with the precipitate was then heated on a water-bath till the precipitate attained a crystalline condition. During the course of heating small amounts of concentrated ammonia were occasionally added to replenish the loss of ammonia due to evaporation, thus preventing the precipitation of any zinc. The crystalline lead precipitate was then filtered and washed by decantation with hot water containing ammonia for at least 3 or 4 times till the wash-water was free from zinc [tested by neutralising the wash-water with dilute nitric acid and then by adding (NH₄)₂HPO₄ solution; if any white precipitate or turbidity appeared in this test, the turbid solution was added to the main bulk of the filtrate and the washing with hot ammoniacal water was carried further till the wash-water gave no such turbidity with (NH₄)₂HPO₄]. The filtrate was collected in a porcelain basin (of about 500 c.c. capacity) and allowed to evaporate on a water-bath after being made almost neutral (very slightly acidic) by adding nitric acid. The precipitate was finally washed on the filter first with warm water and then with a little alcohol which helped a quick drying of the precipitate. It was then dried in an air oven at a temperature of 110°-120°.

The filter paper from which the precipitate had been removed was incinerated to ash in a weighed crucible; dilute nitric acid (a drop or two) was added and then the crucible was gently heated over

a small flame. The main bulk of the precipitate was then transferr- ed to the crucible and heated over the tip of a small flame or in a crucible bath for complete conversion to PbO. An occasional stirring with a stout platinum wire was helpful to this conversion. The crucible with the PbO was then allowed to cool in a desiccator and then weighed.

From the filtrate in the basin, when it reached to a volume of about 150 c.c., zinc was precipitated as $ZnNH_4PO_4$ following the standard method and estimated as such or as $Zn_2P_2O_7$.

In this way with mixtures of different proportions of lead and zinc nitrate solutions, several estimations are made, the results of which are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

Pb (NO ₃) ₂ solution.	Zn (NO ₃) ₂ solution.	H ₂ O ₂	Conc.. NH ₄ OH.	PbO found.	PbO present.	ZnNH ₄ PO ₄ found.	ZnNH ₄ PO ₄ present.
1 c.c.	50 c.c.	2 c.c.	10 c.c.	0.0224 g.	0.0223 g.	1.239 g.	1.235 g.
50	1	20	20	1.119	1.115	0.0248	0.0247
5	50	2	12	0.1114	0.1115	1.238	1.235
25	50	10	12	0.5558	0.5575	1.233	1.235
40	5	16	16	0.8892	0.8920	0.1232	0.1235
10	10	4	10	0.224	0.223	0.248	0.247
10	5	4	6	0.223	0.223	0.1233	0.1235
5	10	2	10	0.1112	0.1115	0.2468	0.2470
5	5	2	6	0.1111	0.1115	0.1235	0.1235
1	1	2	6	0.0222	0.0223	0.0249	0.0247
15	15	6	10	0.3339	0.3345	0.3698	0.3705
2	2	2	6	0.0444	0.0446	0.0492	0.0494
2	40	2	10	0.0448	0.0446	0.9883	0.9880
5	25	2	10	0.1118	0.1115	0.6169	0.6175
						Zn ₂ P ₂ O ₇ found.	Zn ₂ P ₂ O ₇ present
2	20	2	10	0.0445	0.0446	0.4224	0.4222
10	10	4	10	0.2233	0.2230	0.2115	0.2111
40	5	16	16	0.8915	0.8920	0.1053	0.1055

It has also been studied that the precipitations of lead in presence of chlorine ions by hydrogen peroxide and ammonia are quantitative. But these lead precipitates on ignition do not form pure PbO. The nature of these lead precipitates and also that of their ignited products are under investigation, which will form the subject matter of a separate paper.

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